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**The Role of Homoacetogenic bacterial strain in carbon mitigation and
acetic acid production**

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Climate change mitigation has become a primary challenge of the global energy and environmental policy for the last two decades. The threats of extreme climatic events for humans and the sustainability of natural ecosystems have urged policymakers to reduce the increasing anthropogenic emissions of greenhouse gasses (GHG), particularly CO₂, which contributes approximately 65% of the total annual GHG emissions. Apart from its negative effects on the climate, CO₂ is also a valuable resource, containing carbon – one of the most used and processed elements on Earth. It is clear by now that there is a need to remove the surplus of CO₂ from the atmosphere. Not many processes actually exist or are exploited in an industrial scale that sequester CO₂ from the air, despite the fact that CO₂ can be an interesting feedstock for many processes generating valuable chemicals. The main objectives of this research are the isolation of novel homoacetogenic strain and their use in the field of acetic acid production with lignocellulosic material (Rice straw). At present, the production of acetic acid by microbial fermentation uses starchy food crops as raw materials, which is costly and increases waste. Therefore, it is necessary to develop materials with a wider range of sources which will also be a cost-effective measure. Such as biomass, syngas, bio-fermentation gas, fuel combustion exhaust gas and other widely distributed and abundant carbon sources, all of which can be converted into acetic acid under the metabolism of homoacetogenic bacteria. That can not only reduce the cost, but also enable the chemical industry to continue to develop.

Keywords: Greenhouse gases, Lignocellulosic material, Homoacetogens, Acetic acid, Fermentation.